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Enhanced High-Rate Cycling Performance of Nickel-Rich $\text{Li}[\text{Ni}_{0.88}\text{Co}_{0.09}\text{Mn}_{0.03}]\text{O}_2$ Cathodes Through Sc_2O_3 Doping

Parisa Mehdipour^{1,2} | Hossein Rostami^{1,2} | Tao Hu¹ | Ali Margot Huerta-Flores¹ | Pekka Tanskanen³ | Pekka Tynjälä^{1,2} | Ulla Lassi^{1,2}

¹University of Oulu, Research Unit of Sustainable Chemistry, Oulu, Finland | ²University of Jyväskylä, Kokkola University Consortium Chydenius, Kokkola, Finland | ³Research Unit of Process Metallurgy, University of Oulu, Oulu, Finland

Correspondence: Hossein Rostami (H.Rostami64@gmail.com; Hossein.rostamimalkhalifeh@oulu.fi)

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ABSTRACT

Nickel-rich layered oxide cathodes are considered highly promising candidates for next-generation lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), owing to their high energy density. Nevertheless, their practical application remains constrained by limited cycling stability and rate capability. This study explores the influence of Sc_2O_3 doping on the electrochemical performance and structural stability of $\text{LiNi}_{0.88}\text{Co}_{0.09}\text{Mn}_{0.03}\text{O}_2$ (LNCM88). Sc_2O_3 was incorporated at doping levels of 0.5, 1, and 2.5 wt%, and its effects were systematically investigated using several characterization techniques, including scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). These analyses confirmed successful Sc_2O_3 incorporation without significant changes in the cathode morphology. Electrochemical characterizations showed that, although the initial capacity decreased with increasing Sc content, capacity retention and rate performance improved significantly. Notably, the sample doped with 1 wt% Sc_2O_3 demonstrated a discharge capacity of 195.1 mAh g⁻¹ after 100 cycles at 0.1 C, with a retention rate of approximately 93.1%. These findings highlight the efficacy of Sc_2O_3 doping as a viable strategy to enhance the electrochemical properties and commercial potential of nickel-rich layered cathodes in LIB applications. Full cell results revealed that the Sc_2O_3 -doped LNCM88 delivers improved capacity retention, maintaining 83.2% at 1 C after 300 cycles, compared to only 76.4% for the undoped material under identical conditions. High-rate cycling results further demonstrate that 1 wt% Sc doping significantly enhances the durability of LNCM88, making it a promising strategy for improving the performance of nickel-rich layered cathode materials in high-power lithium-ion battery applications.

1 | Introduction

The global initiative to mitigate the environmental impact of transportation and reduce carbon dioxide (CO_2) emissions has catalyzed the rapid growth of the electric vehicle (EV) industry. A key challenge in this transition lies in the development of advanced energy storage technologies, which are critical for enhancing the performance, efficiency, and sustainability of EVs. The increasing demand for EVs underscores the urgent need for high-performance and

environmentally sustainable battery systems to support global carbon reduction targets and facilitate the continued expansion of the EV market [1–3]. Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have emerged as the leading energy storage solution due to their long cycle life, high energy efficiency, adaptability, and superior energy density, coupled with the absence of memory effect. These characteristics position LIBs as a cornerstone technology for next-generation rechargeable systems and a wide range of renewable energy

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applications, including portable electronics, electric vehicles, and grid-scale energy storage devices [4–7].

Cathode materials play a pivotal role in LIBs by providing consistent electrochemical performance, high operating voltage, safety, reliability, and cost-effectiveness. As a result, considerable research efforts have been directed toward enhancing energy density and reducing production costs of LIBs, leading to significant advancements in cathode material development [8].

One of the earliest commercial cathode materials was lithium cobalt oxide (LiCoO₂, LCO), introduced in the 1980s. Despite its widespread use, LCO suffers from several limitations, including high cost, limited energy density, and poor thermal stability, prompting the exploration of alternative cathode chemistries for energy storage applications [9, 10]. In response, lithium nickel cobalt manganese oxide (LiNi_{1-x-y}Co_xMn_yO₂, NCM) was developed in the late 1990s, offering improved capacity, energy density, and structural stability. In NCM cathodes, manganese contributes to longevity and thermal stability, nickel enhances specific capacity, and cobalt supports both thermal stability and capacity [11, 12].

Recent studies have demonstrated that reducing cobalt content while increasing the nickel concentration in NCM materials can further improve specific capacity and address sustainability concerns [13]. Nickel-rich NCM cathodes, with nickel content exceeding 80%, offer high specific discharge capacities (200–220 mAh g⁻¹) and energy densities up to 800 Wh/kg, while simultaneously reducing reliance on cobalt and lowering material costs. However, these nickel-rich compositions face challenges related to safety, thermal stability, and cycle life. Elevated nickel content can destabilize the crystal structure and accelerate capacity degradation, particularly under high temperature and voltage conditions, thereby compromising the overall battery performance [14, 15].

To overcome these limitations, several material engineering strategies have been explored, such as surface modification, ion doping, and morphological control to enhance the performance of Ni-rich layered cathodes. Among these approaches, ion doping introduces trace cations into the crystal lattice without forming secondary phases, thereby stabilizing the structure and improving electrochemical performance [16, 17]. Doping can regulate particle size, inhibit cation mixing, reduce lattice oxygen release, and enhance overall structural integrity. Various dopants, including Al, Cr, Mg, Zr, Ti, Fe, Sn, Ta, and Nb, have been successfully incorporated into Ni-rich NCM cathodes due to their ionic compatibility with the host lattice, typically substituting for Ni, Mn, or Co [18–25].

Sc₂O₃ has recently emerged as a promising dopant for NCM cathodes. Its ionic radius (Sc³⁺: 0.75 Å) allows it to effectively substitute Ni²⁺ (0.69 Å), Co³⁺ (0.545 Å), and Mn⁴⁺ (0.53 Å) within the crystal structure [26]. Sc has also demonstrated viability as a cobalt substitute in perovskite oxides, supporting the development of cobalt-free cathodes for solid oxide fuel cells due to its lower cost, enhanced stability, and improved cathode-electrolyte compatibility [27]. Furthermore, Sc³⁺ doping enhanced the cycling performance of LiMn₂O₄, as its lithium storage properties benefit from the improved structural stability provided by Sc³⁺ ion incorporation [28].

In this study, Sc-doped LiNi_{0.88}Co_{0.09}Mn_{0.03}O₂ (LNCM88-Sc), referred to as LNCM88- % Sc₂O₃, and undoped LiNi_{0.88}Co_{0.09}Mn_{0.03}O₂

(LNCM88), referred to as pristine LNCM88, were examined with respect to their structural, electrochemical, and thermal properties. To the best of our knowledge, the effect of Sc₂O₃ doping on high-Ni NCM88 cathodes has not been extensively investigated.

2 | Experimental

2.1 | Material Synthesis

Spherical precursors of [Ni_{0.88}Co_{0.09}Mn_{0.03}](OH)₂ were synthesized via a co-precipitation reaction in an alkaline solution, employing cathode material precursors. The synthesis was conducted in continuously stirred tank reactors (CSTRs) to ensure homogeneity throughout the process. A 1.5 M metal sulfate solution was prepared by dissolving stoichiometric amounts of NiSO₄·6H₂O, CoSO₄·7H₂O, and MnSO₄·H₂O in deionized (DI) water.

Initially, a 3 L CSTR was charged with NH₃·H₂O, and the co-precipitation reaction was carried out at 50°C under tightly controlled conditions. The pH was maintained at approximately 12.5, and thorough mixing was achieved using a mechanical stirrer operating at 1200 rpm. Simultaneously, 5 M NaOH (aqueous) and ammonia were introduced into the reactor through separate inlets. To prevent undesirable oxidation, the reaction was conducted under a nitrogen atmosphere. Particle growth during the co-precipitation process was monitored by analyzing the particle size distribution (PSD) of the slurry samples, which were periodically collected from the reactor's overflow outlet. The co-precipitation reaction was terminated upon reaching the target D₅₀ particle size. Following the synthesis, the precursors were rinsed and filtered using deionized water, and the filtered slurry was washed with deionized water to remove any residual impurities. The final precipitate was dried overnight at 60°C in a vacuum oven.

During lithiation, excess LiOH was added to ensure uniform lithium incorporation and to mitigate lithium loss during high-temperature calcination. A Li:metal ratio of 1.05:1 was employed. Sc₂O₃ was introduced at concentrations of 0.5 wt%, 1 wt%, and 2.5 wt% during the lithiation process. The mixture was calcined at 780°C for 5 h using a controlled heating ramp of 2.5°C/min in an oxygen-rich environment. After calcination, the material was sieved. It was then ball-milled in a dry chamber to reduce the particle size below 40 μm. Finally, the electrochemical properties of the cleaned, lithiated samples were evaluated using both coin cells and pouch cells. These assessments provided critical insights into the influence of the cleaning process on the electrochemical behavior of the synthesized cathode materials.

2.2 | Characterization Techniques

The tapped density of the precursor powders was measured using an Erweka SVM222 device, following the ISO EN 787/11 standard. During the co-precipitation process, PSD was monitored using a Malvern Mastersizer 3000 (Malvern Panalytical). The chemical composition and stoichiometry of Ni, Mn, and Co were analyzed via inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES). Both the cathode active materials and the synthesized precursors were examined using an Agilent

5110 VDV instrument (Agilent Technologies), equipped with a 1.8 mm semi-demountable torch, a U-series concentric glass nebulizer, a cyclonic double-pass spray chamber, and an SPS-4 autosampler. Measurements were based on the average of five replicates. Yttrium (wavelength 371.029 nm) was used as an internal standard to correct sensitivity drift and matrix effects. Prior to the ICP-OES analysis, solid samples were digested using microwave-assisted digestion according to the EPA3051A standard method, employing a solvent mixture of nitric acid and hydrochloric acid in a 3:1 ratio.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses were performed using the Rigaku SmartLab 9 kW X-ray diffractometer, with cobalt as the radiation source, operating at 40 kV and 135 mA. Diffractograms were collected in the 2θ range of 5–120°, with a step size of 0.01° and a scan rate of 4.06°/min. Peak identification was achieved by comparing the data to the International Centre for Diffraction Data (PDF-4 + 2025) database. Data analysis was conducted using the Rigaku PDXL2 software package, employing the whole powder pattern fitting (WPPF) and Pawley methods for decomposition and least squares refinement to determine crystallite sizes, anisotropy, and distribution. Peak shape modeling was performed using the fundamental parameter (FP) method with continuous scanning and the Cheary–Coelho Axial model, refining the crystallite shape as an ellipsoid and using lognormal distribution for iterative parameter refinement. Additionally, the Rietveld method in PDXL2 was applied for site occupancy analysis. To obtain the Li/Ni mixing, the occupancies of Ni in the 3a site were refined using SmartLab Studio II software. The other occupancies were fixed using the composition obtained from ICP/titration analysis. The XRD of NCM precursor was measured by PANalytical X'Pert Pro XRD equipment using monochromatic $\text{CuK}\alpha 1$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) at 45 kV and 40 mA. Field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) images were acquired using a Zeiss Sigma FESEM at 5 kV for microstructural investigation. Elemental mapping was carried out with a JEOL JXA-8530F Plus field emission electron probe microanalyzer (FE-EPMA). Epoxy samples for EPMA analysis were prepared by combining the epoxy resin and hardener, followed by incorporating the sample powders at room temperature, and then drying and polishing the samples to achieve a smooth surface. Surface chemical analysis was performed using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) with a Thermo Fisher Scientific ESCALAB 250Xi XPS System. The powder samples were placed on a gold sample holder. The high-resolution scan used a pass energy of 20 eV while the survey scan used a pass energy of 150 eV. The monochromatic $\text{AlK}\alpha$ radiation (1486.7 eV) operated at 20 mA and 15 kV with an X-ray spot size of 900 μm . The Li, Ni, Co, Mn, Sc, O, and C were measured for all samples, and the measurement data were analyzed by Avantage V5 program. The charge compensation was carried out by applying the C1s at 284.8 eV as a reference to determine the presented spectra and calibrate the binding energies. All XRD, FESEM, EPMA, and XPS measurements were conducted at the Centre for Material Analysis, University of Oulu, Finland.

2.3 | Electrochemical Characterization

The electrode foils and battery cells were fabricated in a dry room environment under controlled conditions. The preparation of the cathode slurry involved utilizing a Thinky ARE-250 planetary mixer. The composition of the slurry comprised 4 wt%

poly(vinylidene fluoride) (Kureha #1100), 4 wt% conductive carbon black (Timcal C45), and 92 wt% active material. The solvent was 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (Alfa Aesar, anhydrous, 99.5%). The slurry was uniformly applied to aluminum foil using 100 μm applicators and subsequently dried on a hot plate at 50°C for 1 h dried in a vacuum oven at 120°C overnight. The cathode foil was calendared three times before coin cell assembly. The active material of the coin cells was a 14 mm LNCM88 cathode, while the counter electrode was a 12 mm metallic lithium. Ethyl methyl carbonate (EMC), dimethyl carbonate (DMC), and ethylene carbonate (EC) were mixed 1:1:1 with 1 M LiPF₆ as the electrolyte. These cells ran at a certain C-rate and underwent 100 charge-discharge cycles at 25°C. For the first two cycles of the charging process, a steady current was supplied until the voltage reached 4.3 V. This was followed by a steady voltage phase until the current dropped to 0.015 C. The limit was increased to 0.02 C for the remaining cycles. A constant voltage was provided until the current decreased to 0.015 C after the first two discharge cycles, which employed a constant current of 0.1 C until the voltage hit 2.6 V. Until 3.0 V was reached, subsequent discharges were carried out at a steady current. For the full cells, the cell included a graphite anode (Hitachi) and an electrolyte composed of 1.15 M LiPF₆ in a mixture of EC:DMC:EMC in a 2:4:4 ratio, along with 1 wt% vinylene carbonate. The N/P ratio was 1.1 with a cathode loading of 13–14 mg/cm², an anode loading of 7–8 mg/cm². Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was performed using the Interface 1010E Potentiostat (Gamry Instruments, Warminster, PA, USA), over a frequency range of 80 mHz to 100 kHz, at room temperature.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Characterization of Precursors and Cathode Samples

Figure 1a shows the XRD patterns of the NCM88 precursor. These patterns closely resemble those of pure Ni(OH)₂, indicating the presence of a hexagonal crystal structure [29]. This structural configuration reflects the atomic arrangement within the analyzed compounds. In the Ni(OH)₂ structure, partial substitution of Ni²⁺ ions by Co²⁺ and Mn²⁺ ions was observed, suggesting the incorporation of Co and Mn into the crystal lattice and the formation of the NCM88 compound.

After calcination, Figure 1b presents the XRD patterns of undoped and Sc-doped LNCM88 samples, with doping concentrations of 1 wt% and 2.5 wt%. All XRD patterns were consistent with a hexagonal $\alpha\text{-NaFeO}_2$ structure, assigned to the R $\bar{3}m$ space group. The diffraction peaks are sharp and well-defined, with no significant shifts or changes in the lattice parameters (see Table 1). The distinct splitting of the (006)/(102) and (018)/(110) peaks confirms the preservation of the layered structure after calcination. As seen in Table 1, the unit-cell volume and c lattice parameter increase slightly with increasing Sc content. This expansion can be attributed to the substitution of larger Sc³⁺ ions for smaller transition-metal cations in the R $\bar{3}m$ lattice, which induces local lattice distortion and increases the transition-metal slab thickness [30]. The changes in unit-cell volume clearly indicate that Sc ions, which have a larger ionic radius, are successfully incorporated into the bulk crystal

FIGURE 1 | (a) XRD of the NCM88 precursor, and (b) XRD patterns of undoped and Sc-doped LNCM88 samples.

TABLE 1 | Lattice parameters and Sc content of undoped and doped LNCM88 samples.

Sample	a (Å)	c (Å)	c/a	Volume	I(003)/I(104)	Ni ²⁺ in Li layer (%)	Sc (mg/g)
LNCM88	2.8734	14.1880	4.9378	101.4457	0.754	3.3	< 0.001
LNCM88-0.5% Sc	2.8732	14.1873	4.9378	101.4484	0.873	3	4.9
LNCM88-1% Sc	2.8742	14.1924	4.9379	101.5402	0.889	2	9
LNCM88-2.5% Sc	2.8749	14.1962	4.9380	101.6166	0.931	1.8	24.3

structure of LNCM88 by substituting for Ni²⁺, Co³⁺, and Mn⁴⁺. A key feature of the diffraction pattern is the intensity ratio of the (003) and (104) reflections, I(003)/I(104), which is commonly used as a qualitative indicator of Li/Ni cation mixing in layered oxide cathodes. In general, a higher I(003)/I(104) ratio reflects a lower degree of cation disorder and better preservation of the layered structure, since Li/Ni mixing reduces the scattering contrast between the lithium and transition-metal layers. As summarized in Table 1, the I(003)/I(104) ratio increases from 0.75 for pristine LNCM88 to 0.87, 0.89, and 0.93 for the 0.5 wt%, 1 wt%, and 2.5 wt% Sc-doped samples, respectively,

suggesting a progressive reduction in cation disorder with increasing Sc content. To obtain a quantitative estimation of Li/Ni mixing, Rietveld refinement was performed by refining the Ni occupancy in the Li (3a) site. The detailed refinement parameters are provided in Table S1, while the calculated Li/Ni mixing values are summarized in Table 1. The results indicate that Li/Ni mixing decreases from 3.3% in pristine LNCM88 to 3.0%, 2.0%, and 1.8% for the 0.5%, 1%, and 2.5% Sc-doped samples, respectively, consistent with the trend observed in the I(003)/I(104) ratio. The refinement results indicate a decrease in the Li/Ni mixing after the incorporation of Sc dopant. Due to

the larger ionic radius of Sc^{3+} (0.745 Å), the transition metal cation layer increases in size, causing a steric that makes the migration of Ni^{2+} into the Li layer energetically unfavorable. This effect is beneficial because nickel migration into the lithium layer reduces Li^+ diffusion and electrochemical performance.

SEM was used to investigate the morphology of both the precursor and the lithiated samples. As shown in Figure S1a–c, the precursor exhibits a uniform distribution of spherical particles at low magnification (a), with consistent size and shape. At higher magnification (b), the NCM88 precursor reveals a well-defined spherical morphology with a hierarchical micro/nanostructure, characterized by densely packed nanosheets separated by moderate gaps. This architecture combines the benefits of both nano- and micron-scale particles: nanoparticles enhance Li^+ diffusion by increasing the active surface area, thereby improving capacity and rate capability, while micrometer-sized particles contribute to higher tap density and better cyclic stability by minimizing side reactions with the electrolyte. Furthermore, this structure is amenable to doping, allowing for potential performance enhancements [31]. Figure 2 illustrates the morphology and microstructure of undoped and Sc-doped LNCM88 samples, captured at varying magnifications. Following lithiation, both undoped (Figure 2a,b) and Sc-doped (Figure 2c–h) LNCM88 samples retain the overall spherical morphology of the precursor. However, the surface structure of the nanoparticles changed from thin nanosheets into a more block-like structure after the calcination. No significant differences in particle distribution or surface morphology are observed between the undoped and doped LNCM88 samples. In summary, calcination induces a transformation of the nanosheet structure into a block-like morphology, but Sc_2O_3 doping does not produce noticeable changes in the overall particle morphology.

High-resolution SEM analysis confirms that Sc_2O_3 doping up to 2.5 wt% does not significantly alter the primary particle size or morphology of LNCM88, indicating that the electrochemical improvements arise mainly from structural and interfacial stabilization rather than morphological changes. The preserved spherical morphology and hierarchical microstructure are expected to facilitate lithium-ion transport and maintain structural stability during cycling.

Figure 3 illustrates the changes in the valence states of transition metals and oxygen elements as determined by XPS analysis. Figure S2 presents the XPS spectra of the O 1s, Ni 2p, Co 2p, Mn 2p, Sc 2p, C 1s, and Li 1s orbitals for both the LNCM88, LNCM88-1% Sc and LNCM88-2.5% Sc samples. In the Ni 2p spectra (Figure 3a), two satellite peaks are observed, with the

main peaks of Ni $2p_{3/2}$ and Ni $2p_{1/2}$ located at binding energies of 855.9 and 873.5 eV, respectively. Upon Sc 1% doping, these peaks shift slightly to lower binding energies 855.5 and 873.2 eV indicating a change in the local chemical environment of Ni ions. Figure 3b shows Co 2p spectra, where Co $2p_{3/2}$ and Co $2p_{1/2}$ peaks appear at 779.8 and 794.8 eV, respectively. These values are consistent with the Co^{3+} oxidation state, as typically observed in LiCoO_2 . For Mn 2p, a broad binding energy range between 641 and 643 eV is detected in both LNCM88 and LNCM88-1% Sc samples, suggesting the presence of Mn^{4+} . Notably, Sc doping results in a decrease in the intensities of the Mn 2p, Ni 2p, and Co 2p peaks, which can be attributed to the reduced relative concentrations of these transition metals due to partial substitution by Sc. Figure 3d highlights the Sc 2p region. The Sc 2p XPS spectra show two well-resolved doublets. The first one exhibits peaks at 401.0 eV ($2p_{3/2}$) and 405.3 eV ($2p_{1/2}$). These peaks are consistent with Sc^{3+} incorporated in LNCM lattice, where Sc^{3+} is present in a metal-coordinated environment, substituting the B site, rather than Li^+ sites in the layered structure. The second doublet shows peaks at 402.5 eV ($2p_{3/2}$) and 406.5 eV ($2p_{1/2}$), and they are consistent with the values reported for bulk Sc_2O_3 , suggesting that a minor fraction of Sc may exist in an oxide-like local environment, while the majority is incorporated into the LNCM lattice [32]. These two environments demonstrate that the Sc dopant is incorporated in the LNCM lattice, while a minor fraction is present as a separate oxide. This is consistent with the results observed by XRD. These findings demonstrate effective Sc doping and support the structural integrity of LNCM88, which may contribute to enhanced functional properties of the material.

Figure 4 presents EPMA elemental mapping, highlighting the composition and spatial distribution of key elements within the samples. The maps illustrate the presence of O, Ni, Co, Mn, and Sc, showing their uniform distribution throughout the material. Notably, the Sc map in Figure 4b confirms successful incorporation of Sc into the doped sample (LNCM88-Sc1%), as evidenced by its homogeneous distribution. This comparison demonstrates that Sc doping was achieved without compromising the elemental uniformity of the material, thereby preserving its structural integrity.

3.2 | Electrochemical Performance of Cathode Materials

As discussed in Section 3.1, Sc doping reduces Li/Ni cation mixing, which contributes to improved structural stability

FIGURE 2 | SEM images of (a, b) undoped LNCM88, (c, d) 0.5 wt% Sc-doped LNCM88, (e, f) 1 wt% Sc-doped LNCM88 and (g, h) 2.5 wt% Sc-doped LNCM88.

FIGURE 3 | The XPS spectra of the LNCM and LNCM88-1% Sc.

during cycling. Therefore, the electrochemical performance of the prepared cathodes was systematically evaluated to determine how these structural modifications affect battery behavior. Figure 5 and Table 2 present the electrochemical performance of the cathode samples, evaluated through galvanostatic charge/discharge testing. Measurements were conducted at a rate of 0.1 C within a voltage window of 2.6–4.3 V, focusing on both initial and 100th-cycle capacities. The results showed that the pristine LNCM88 sample exhibited the highest initial charge and discharge capacities, with a charge capacity of 239 mAh g^{-1} and a discharge capacity of 217.1 mAh g^{-1} . However, as the Sc doping concentration increased, the initial discharge capacity gradually decreased. In particular, the LNCM88-2.5% Sc sample showed significantly lower initial charge and discharge

capacities compared to the other samples. After 100 cycles, notable differences in capacity retention were observed (Figure 5b). The pristine LNCM88 sample experienced a reduction in discharge capacity from an initial 216.4 to 181.3 mAh g^{-1} , corresponding to a retention rate of 83.8%. In contrast, the Sc-doped samples demonstrate significantly improved performance at 0.1 C. Specifically, the LNCM88-1% Sc sample retained a discharge capacity of 195.1 mAh g^{-1} , achieving a retention rate of 93.1%, indicating that 1% Sc doping effectively enhances structural stability and capacity retention over cycling. Similarly, LNCM88-2.5% Sc sample exhibited a retention rate of 92.9% at 0.1 C, outperforming the undoped sample despite its lower initial capacity. These results suggest that moderate Sc doping improves long-term electrochemical

FIGURE 4 | Elemental mapping results of Ni, Co, Mn, Sc, and O for the (a) LNCM88 and (b) LNCM88-1% Sc.

stability, with 1% Sc offering an optimal balance between initial capacity and retention performance.

Figure 6a illustrates the electrochemical cycling performance of all as-prepared samples at 2 C and at 25°C within a voltage window of 2.6–4.5 V. During the initial cycles, discharge capacities decreased with increasing Sc content. However, the 0.5% and 1% Sc-doped samples exhibited better cycling performance compared to the pristine LNCM88 sample. Notably, the LNCM88-1% Sc sample delivered the highest discharge capacity of 143.0 mAh g^{-1} , with a retention rate of 78.1% after 100 cycles at 2 C. In contrast, the pristine LNCM88 sample showed only a discharge capacity of 105.3 mAh g^{-1} , and a retention of 55.3%, while the LNCM88-2.5% Sc sample demonstrated the lowest performance, with a discharge capacity of 95.7 mAh g^{-1} and capacity retention 53.1%. This improvement shows that, although the LNCM88-2.5% Sc sample exhibits a higher $I(003)/I(104)$ ratio, which generally indicates reduced Li/Ni cation mixing and improved layered ordering, this parameter alone does not fully determine long-term electrochemical stability, particularly at higher dopant concentrations. Several factors may contribute to the lower capacity retention of the 2.5% Sc-doped sample compared to the 1% Sc-doped material, at higher Sc contents, the substitution of Sc^{3+} into the transition-metal layer can introduce local lattice strain and disrupt the optimal TM-O bonding environment. While moderate 1% Sc doping stabilizes the layered structure, excessive incorporation may weaken structural coherence during repeated Li^+ insertion/extraction, accelerating degradation

during cycling. Overall, these results indicate that while Sc doping effectively suppresses Li/Ni mixing, there exists an optimal dopant concentration. This indicates that moderate Sc doping provides improved structural stability during cycling or interfacial side effects, whereas excessive doping (2.5 wt%) leads to diminished electrochemical performance despite improved crystallographic ordering indicators. Figure 6b presents the performance rate of the samples, evaluated systematically using the following testing protocol: the samples were charged at a constant rate of 0.5 C, followed by discharging at varying rates of 0.1 C, 0.5 C, 1 C, 2 C, and 5 C over five cycles for each rate. The results reveal that the Sc-doped samples exhibit enhanced rate capability compared to the pristine LNCM88, indicating improved electrochemical stability and faster charge/discharge kinetics in the doped samples. Figure 6c compares the high-rate cycling performance of LNCM88, 0.5% Sc-doped, 1% Sc-doped, and 2.5% Sc-doped cathodes at a charge–discharge rate of 3 C within the voltage range of 2.7–4.3 V. All samples exhibit an initial capacity decline during cycling; however, clear differences in capacity retention are observed depending on the Sc doping level. The 1% Sc-doped sample demonstrates the most stable performance, delivering an initial discharge capacity of $139.11 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$ and retaining $121.05 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$ after 100 cycles. The 0.5% Sc-doped electrode shows an initial discharge capacity of $138.15 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$, which decreases to $117.18 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$, indicating moderate capacity fading. In contrast, although the 2.5% Sc-doped sample exhibits a comparable initial capacity of $139.82 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$, its discharge capacity decreases more significantly to $111.15 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$ after 100 cycles. These results suggest that while

FIGURE 5 | Charging/discharging curves of undoped and Sc-doped LNCM88 samples: (a) first cycle, (b) after 100 cycles at 0.1 C, 25°C.

Sc incorporation generally enhances high-rate performance compared to the pristine LNCM88, excessive Sc doping (2.5 wt%) introduces kinetic or interfacial limitations that accelerate capacity decay under high current densities. Consequently, 1 wt% Sc doping provides the optimal balance between structural stabilization and fast Li^+ transport during high-rate cycling.

To further assess the impact of Sc doping on long-term electrochemical performance, Figure 6d presents the long-term cycling performance of LNCM88-based full cells with a graphite anode at a current rate of 1 C. The pristine LNCM88 full cell exhibits a capacity retention of approximately 76.4% after 300 cycles, indicating significant performance degradation during prolonged cycling. In comparison, Sc-doped electrodes show improved cycling stability. The 0.5% Sc-doped sample retains 82.0% of its initial capacity after 300 cycles, while the 2.5% Sc-doped electrode exhibits a lower retention of 74.5%, suggesting accelerated degradation at higher dopant levels. Notably, the 1% Sc-doped LNCM88 demonstrates the best long-term stability,

maintaining 83.2% capacity retention after 300 cycles. These results confirm that moderate Sc doping effectively enhances full-cell cycling durability, whereas excessive Sc incorporation leads to diminished retention despite initial performance benefits.

To further understand the influence of Sc doping on lithium-ion transport kinetics, PITT measurements were conducted. Additionally, to assess the impact of Sc doping on lithium-ion transport, the Li^+ diffusion coefficient D_{Li^+} was calculated from the PITT data after cycling. Performing the PITT measurement after several charge-discharge cycles is important because it reflects the actual kinetic behavior of the electrode under realistic operating conditions. During cycling, structural changes such as cation mixing, surface reconstruction, or particle cracking can occur, all of which influence the ease of Li^+ migration. Therefore, the D_{Li^+} values obtained after cycling provide a more accurate representation of the electrode's long-term electrochemical performance. The D_{Li^+} value is

TABLE 2 | Electrochemical analysis results for the as-prepared samples at 3.0–4.3 V.

Sample	0.1 C charge 4.3 V, 1st (mAh g ⁻¹)	0.1 C discharge 3.0 V, (mAh g ⁻¹)	0.1 C discharge 3.0 V, 100th, (mAh g ⁻¹)	Retention (0.1 C) after 100 cycles (%)
LNCM88	238.3	216.4	181.3	83.8
LNCM88-0.5% Sc	238.1	210.1	191.2	91
LNCM88-1% Sc	235.5	209.5	195.1	93.1
LNCM88-2.5% Sc	229.8	202.3	188.1	92.9

FIGURE 6 | (a) Cycling performance at 2 C for all as-prepared samples at 25°C, (b) Rate capability for all as-prepared samples at 25°C, (c) High-rate cycling performance at 3 C within a voltage range of 2.7–4.3 V and 25°C (d) Full cell cycling performance for LNCM88 and LNCM88-1% Sc at a voltage range of 2.8–4.2 V.

determined from the slope of the linear segment in the $\ln[I(t)]$ versus t curve:

$$D_{\text{Li}^+} = -\frac{4L^2}{\pi^2} \frac{d \ln[I(t)]}{dt}$$

L represents the lithium-ion diffusion length, which is approximately equal to the primary particle size of the material. Both samples exhibit similar D_{Li^+} curves, and the D_{Li^+} values increase as the potential rises. A higher D_{Li^+} indicates faster Li^+ mobility and lower kinetic resistance during lithiation and delithiation. As shown in Figure 7, the LNCM88-1% Sc sample exhibited higher D_{Li^+} than the pristine material, demonstrating improved Li^+ transport kinetics in the Sc-doped sample even after cycling. This directly supports the improved rate capability and cycling stability observed electrochemically.

EIS was performed to further evaluate the influence of Sc doping on interfacial resistance and charge-transfer kinetics during cycling. Figure S3a and S3b show the Nyquist plots obtained after the 1st and 100th cycles. In these plots, the semicircles observed in the high- and medium-frequency regions correspond to the interface resistance (R_f) and charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), respectively, while the straight line in the low-frequency region reflects the lithium-ion diffusion coefficient (D_{Li^+}).

The fitted EIS parameters, summarized in Table 3, reveal that the pristine LNCM88 sample initially exhibited lower R_f and R_{ct} values compared to the Sc-doped samples. However, after 100 cycles, both R_f and R_{ct} increased for all samples. Notably, the R_{ct} of pristine LNCM88 rose sharply from 35.1 to 576.2 Ω , indicating significant interfacial degradation. In contrast, the LNCM88-1% Sc sample showed a much smaller increase in R_{ct} ,

FIGURE 7 | Transient current plots obtained from PITT measurements: $\ln(I)$ versus t for (a) LNCM88 and (b) LNCM88-1% Sc. (c) The corresponding Li^+ diffusion coefficients (D_{Li^+}) extracted at different potentials for LNCM88 and LNCM88-1% Sc.

TABLE 3 | The fitted EIS parameters for LNCM88, LNCM88-1% Sc and LNCM88-2.5% Sc samples after 1st and 100th cycles.

Sample	1st		100th	
	R_f	R_{ct}	R_f	R_{ct}
LNCM88	10.7	35.1	17.5	576.2
LNCM88-1% Sc	11.1	37.5	4.8	108.9
LNCM88-2.5% Sc	37.3	48.9	17.8	502.1

from 37.5 to 108.9 Ω . These results confirm that Sc doping effectively stabilizes the electrode-electrolyte interface, suppressing detrimental interfacial reactions and mitigating the formation of resistive surface layers. The improved performance of LNCM88-1% Sc can be attributed to Sc's role in reinforcing the structural integrity of the cathode material, thereby reducing degradation mechanisms during prolonged cycling. Overall, the smaller increases in R_f and R_{ct} observed in the Sc-doped samples contribute to better interfacial stability and enhanced electrochemical performance, particularly under extended cycling conditions.

4 | Conclusions

In this study, the effect of Sc_2O_3 doping on the structural properties of NCM88 and electrochemical performance was studied. Based on the results, Sc_2O_3 doping preserves the morphology of LNCM88 while improving its electrochemical stability. Electrochemical testing revealed that

although Sc doping led to a small reduction in initial discharge capacity, it markedly improved capacity retention, rate capability, and long-term cycling stability. Among the tested compositions, the NCM88-1%Sc exhibited the most favorable electrochemical stability and capacity retention, indicating an optimal balance between performance and structural integrity.

The improved performance of LNCM88 with 1% Sc is attributed to structural stabilization from Sc incorporation, which reinforces the cathode's integrity, minimizes the formation of unstable surface layers, and suppresses degradation during cycling. This stabilization reduces the growth of resistance factors (R_f and R_{ct}) over time, as shown by EIS results, thereby improving interfacial stability and delivering superior electrochemical performance. These results indicate that Sc doping is a promising and commercially viable strategy for improving the performance of Ni-rich layered cathodes in next-generation high-energy and high-power LIBs.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available on Zenodo via this link: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/17264982>.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Fig. S1: SEM images of NCM88 precursor at different magnification.

Fig. S2: The XPS spectra of the LNCM, LNCM88-1% Sc and LNCM88-

2.5% Sc. **Fig. S3:** Nyquist plots of the LNCM88, LNCM88-1% Sc, and

LNCM88-2.5% Sc after (a) 1st and (b) 100 cycles. **Table S1:** Full Rietveld

refinement parameters for pristine and Sc-doped LNCM88 samples.